

[Jour. Indian Chem. Soc., Vol. 26, No. 1, 1949]

PRODUCTION OF JOSHI EFFECT IN SULPHUR DIOXIDE UNDER SILENT ELECTRIC DISCHARGE

BY G. S. DESHMUKH AND U. S. DEAR

Under ozoniser discharge SO_2 shows a marked *negative Joshi effect* (33% at maximum). At constant applied kV, it decreases with pressure p beyond a certain limit. At constant p , increase of kV decreases it. *Positive Joshi effect* $+\Delta i$, is observed at low kV. It decreases precipitously by a small increase in kV; further increase first abolishes it and then inverts it to $-\Delta i$. 'Ageing' under discharge diminishes the effect markedly due to SO_3 condensation from SO_2 decomposition, since a pre-formed SO_3 film inhibits $-\Delta i$ in SO_2 , that of NaOH enhances it. Results support Joshi's theory of the surface origin of the phenomenon.

Soon after the discovery of the negative Joshi effect $-\Delta i$ (Joshi, *Proc. Indian Sci. Cong.*, 1943, Part II, pp. 70-75), an instantaneous and reversible photodiminution of the current i in a number of elementary gases, the positive Joshi effect, $+\Delta i$, was observed in iodine vapour in the presence of a surface film of KI and KI_3 (Joshi and Murthy, *Proc. Indian Sci. Cong.*, 1942, Part III, p. 64), in nitrogen peroxide (Joshi and Visvanathan, *ibid.*, p. 66), oxygen (Joshi and Cherian, *ibid.*, p. 58) and bromine (Deshmukh and Sirsikar, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, communicated). The presence of impurities and 'wall effect' in electrically excited system had a marked influence on the production of the Joshi effect (Shukla, *Proc. Indian Sci. Cong.*, 1948, Part III, *Chem. Sec.*, p. 12). Sulphur dioxide gas under silent electric discharge was found to produce as decomposition products, annular films of sulphur trioxide and sulphur, in addition to the undecomposed gas, oxygen and two other unidentified solids (Joshi and Sharma, *J. chem. phys.*, 1943, 31, 511). It was of interest therefore to extend the observations of the phenomenon to sulphur dioxide gas and to investigate the rôle of its products of decomposition on the production of the Joshi effect.

EXPERIMENTAL

The general arrangement of the apparatus and the electrical circuit employed are shown in Fig. 1. Sulphur dioxide gas was prepared by the action of concentrated sulphuric acid on sodium bisulphite in A. The gas was led slowly through a series of tubes charged with P_2O_5 and CaCl_2 , and stocked in the reservoir R. It was next purified by freezing it in the traps D_1 and D_2 , cooled by liquid air. The uncondensable portion was removed with the tötpler. The

condensed SO_2 in D_2 was then allowed to evaporate. The first and the last fractions of the gas were rejected ; the middle fraction was stored in R.

FIG 1

The discharge was produced in the annular space of a Siemens' type (glass) ozoniser ; two such ozonisers were used (see Fig. 1). The ozoniser was connected through the drying tubes to the reservoir R by proper manipulation of the taps T_4 and T_5 , and directly to the mercury manometer and the toppler through the tap T_6 . A given series of experiments was commenced only after the entire assembly had maintained a satisfactory vacuum for at least 48 hours.

The ozoniser was excited by a transformer discharge of 50 cycles frequency in the primary supply. The primary potential V (except when too low) was recorded with an A. C. voltmeter ; the secondary potential in kilo-volts (r. m. s.) kV , was calculated from a knowledge of V and the step-up ratio of the transformer, viz., 267. The system was irradiated transversely to the ozoniser axis, by operating a shutter between it and two 100 watts incandescent (glass) bulbs run at 220 volts. The inner electrode of the ozoniser was connected to the transformer secondary ; the other was earthed. The discharged current, i , was measured with a milliammeter or a reflection type galvanometer actuated by a metal-oxide rectifier, introduced in the low tension line of the ozoniser circuit. From observations of the current i_D , when the ozoniser was screened from the light, and when exposed to it i_L , the net joshi effect, Δi , is given by $i_D - i_L$; its relative value $\% \Delta i$ is $100 \Delta i / i_D$.

JOSHI EFFECT IN SULPHUR DIOXIDE UNDER SILENT ELECTRIC DISCHARGE 21

As found by Joshi and Sharma (*loc. cit.*) the dielectric strength of SO_2 was high. Decompositions were produced therefore at moderate gas pressures within the range of 9 to 180 mm. up to 8 kV applied to the ozoniser. The general progress of the decomposition, as followed by the pressure-time observations, showed a progressive but small fall of pressure during the initial and limited period of exposure to the discharge. Further continuation of the discharge resulted in a state during which the pressure decreased extremely slowly. In agreement with the results of Joshi and Sharma (*loc. cit.*) the decomposition under silent discharge of SO_2 gave SO_3 , free sulphur, oxygen and traces of two solid products (not identified).

The procedure in respect of observations of the Joshi effect in SO_2 , as indicated by the general results mentioned above, was as follows: The purified gas was admitted into the annular space of the ozoniser at a low pressure. The values of i_D and i_L were then noted at a series of increasing applied potential kV. This was changed to the next higher value only when the rate of decomposition became negligibly small as judged by the (sensible) constancy of the pressure of the decomposition mixture. Thus *e.g.*, during the first series of results under Table I, the extent of decomposition of SO_2 corresponded to a pressure change of only 1.5 mm. *i.e.* about 6.2%. The contents of the annular space were tóplered out and a fresh sample of the purified gas (from the same stock as before) was introduced at a pressure slightly higher than the previous value. Results for i_D , i_L , Δi and $\% \Delta i$ were recorded once more (at $p=30$ mm.), until, as in the previous series, a state of practically arrested decomposition ensued; the final pressure diminution now produced was 6 mm. *i.e.* 20% of the initial pressure. After this, once again the gaseous products were tóplered out, fresh SO_2 introduced at a higher pressure, and so on, in successive series. Table I contains data of one of a number of groups of such results obtained. For want of an A. C. voltmeter during this stage of work, results are given for the total ozoniser current in milli-amps, mA. These values served as an index of the corresponding variation of the actual potential applied to the ozoniser.

The series of data in Table II were obtained in a way similar to that followed in Table I. The ozoniser now used was different from that in Table I; its electrodes were fitted with a ground joint, instead of a sealed one (as in Table I). In this series the pressure of SO_2 was increased progressively over the range of 9 to 47 mm., the exciting potential being varied from 1.8 to 8 kV. Table II is typical of a series of results in which the *positive* Joshi effect (*i.e.* a photo-increase of the current i) was observed at low exciting kV.

For reasons explained later, it was of interest to investigate the production of Joshi effect in SO_2 in presence of certain annular films, *viz.*, sodium sulphate, sodium hydroxide and mercuric chloride. For this part of the work a new ozoniser (*vide infra*), also fitted with a ground joint, was employed. The inside surface of the outer tube and the outer surface of the inner tube were

smearred carefully with concentrated aqueous solution of each of the above substances. The electrodes were then fitted together and the entire system exhausted *slowly* but completely over the topler. Purified SO_2 was then admitted in successive samples at increasing pressures and i_D , i_L , Δi and $\% \Delta i$ were observed with each electrode film as described in Table II. These results for the three films mentioned above, in contact with SO_2 in the pressure range of 16 to 60 mm. and excited under the discharge at 1 to 6 kV, are recorded in Table III.

TABLE I
Ozoniser A

Initial pressure p of SO_2 —24 mm. Diminution in p —1.5 mm., 6.3%.				
i (in mA).	i_D .	i_L .	Δi .	$\% \Delta i$.
0.04	8.4	6.4	-2.0	-24
0.06	15.6	13.6	-2.0	-13
0.10	25.6	22.6	-3.0	-11.7
0.16	42.0	38.6	-3.4	-8.1
0.20	52.0	46.0	-6.0	-11.5
0.24	59.4	55.4	-4.0	-6.7
0.26	109.4	104.4	-5.0	-4.6
0.30*	129.0	125.0	-4.0	-3.1
Initial p of SO_2 —30 mm. Diminution in p —6 mm., 20%				
0.10	15	10	-0.5	-3.3
0.20	12.0	10.0	-2.0	-17
0.26	14.0	12.0	-2.0	-14
0.30	27.0	23.5	-3.5	-13
0.34*	32.5	30.0	-2.5	-8
Initial p —55 mm. Diminution in p —8 mm., 15%				
0.04	7.2	6.6	-0.6	-8
0.06	15.0	14.4	-0.6	-4.0
0.08	23.0	22.2	-0.8	-3.5
0.10	34.0	33.4	-0.6	-1.8
0.14	58.4	58.0	-0.4	-0.7
0.16	62.0	61.8	-0.2	-0.3
0.18	71.2	71.0	-0.2	-0.3
0.20	79.8	79.6	-0.2	-0.25
0.24*	105.4	105.4

* Decomposition products were toplered out at this stage and fresh SO_2 from the same stock was introduced.

TABLE II

Ozoniser B

 Initial p of $\text{SO}_2=9$ mm. Diminution in $p=1$ mm., 11%.

kV.	i (mA).	i_D .	i_L .	Δi .	$\% \Delta i$.
1.8	0.06	21.4	26.0	+3.6	+17
2.3	0.08	28.0	30.0	+2.0	+7
3.2	0.10	37.0	37.0
4.5	0.12	45.0	44.0	-1.0	-2
5.3	0.14	55.4	54.0	-1.4	-2.5
5.9	0.16	67.4	68.0	+0.6	+0.8
6.2	0.18	78.0	72.4	-5.6	-7.2
6.9	0.20	84.0	83.4	-0.6	-0.7
8.0*	0.24	98.0	98.0

 Initial $p=18$ mm. Diminution in $p=2$ mm., 11%

1.8	0.04	16.6	18.6	+2.0	+12
2.1	0.06	28.0	31.0	+3.0	+11
2.7	0.08	43.8	47.0	+3.4	+8
4.1	0.10	61.0	61.0
4.9	0.14	73.8	71.6	-2.0	-3
5.6	0.16	85.6	80.6	-5.0	-6
6.5	0.20	112.0	103.0	-9.0	-8
6.9*	0.22	122.0	116.0	-6.0	-5

* Decomposition products were tapered out at this stage and fresh SO_2 from the same stock was introduced.

At successive higher pressures of SO_2 (i. e. 42 mm., 47 mm. etc.) the Joshi effect was not observed.

TABLE III

 Ozoniser C (with a coat of Na_2SO_4).

 Initial p of $\text{SO}_2=16$ mm. Diminution in $p=2$ mm., 12.5%.

kV.	i (mA).	i_D .	i_L .	Δi .	$\% \Delta i$.
1.7	0.04	22.0	19.4	-2.6	-12
2.5	0.08	38.6	37.8	-0.8	-2
4.2*	0.12	56.4	56.4

 Initial p of $\text{SO}_2=31$ mm. Diminution in $p=7$ mm., 23.6%

1.6	0.04	11.6	9.6	-2.0	-17
2.8	0.08	36.0	34.6	-1.4	-4
3.9	0.12	56.0	55.0	-1.0	-2
4.9	0.16	82.4	81.4	-1.0	-1
5.6*	0.20	108.0	108.0

TABLE III (contd.)
Ozoniser C (with a coat of NaOH)

Initial p of SO_2 —26 mm. Diminution in p —2 mm, 7.7%						
kV.	i (mA)	i_D	i_L	Δi	$\% \Delta i$	
1.3	0.04	20.0	17.0	- 3.0	-15	
2.1	0.08	41.0	35.0	- 6.0	-14	
2.9	0.12	69.0	59.0	-10.0	-14	
4.0	0.16	90.0	71.0	-19.0	-21	
5.1*	0.20	111.0	93.0	-18.0	-12	

* Decomposition products were tapered out at this stage and fresh SO_2 from the same stock was introduced.

Initial p of SO_2 —59 mm. Diminution in p —9 mm., 15.2%						
kV.	i (mA)	i_D	i_L	Δi	$\% \Delta i$	
2.8	0.04	15.0	14.0	- 1.0	- 7	
2.9	0.08	38.0	32.0	- 6.0	-16	
3.7	0.12	66.0	57.0	- 9.0	-14	
4.7	0.16	90.0	79.0	-11.0	-12	
5.7*	0.20	129.0	123.0	- 6.0	- 5	

DISCUSSION

Tables I to III and Fig. 2 which contain but typical results, show that both the positive and (the more familiar) negative Joshi effect, $\pm \Delta i$ are

FIG. 2

produced in SO_2 under electric discharge. It is seen that at a constant applied kV the Joshi effect is first increased and then reduced by increasing the gas

pressure, p . Thus *e.g.*, at a kV corresponding to 0.1 mA (see Table I) the relative Joshi effect, $\% \Delta i$, increases from 8 to 30 as p is increased from 24 to 30 mm., a further increase of pressure to 55 mm. reduces $\% \Delta i$ to 2.0. The relative effect was maximum at low exciting potential and decreased by increasing the applied kV. Both these deductions are in agreement with the generality of the findings from these laboratories in regard to Δi phenomenon. The possible influence of the products of decomposition of SO_2 under the discharge on its characteristic Joshi effect is considered later. It may be recalled that soon after the discovery of the negative Joshi effect, the positive effect, $+\Delta i$ was observed in iodine vapour excited in the presence of a surface film of $\text{KI} + \text{KI}_3$ in nitrogen peroxide, oxygen, air and bromine (Joshi and co-workers, *loc. cit.*). Data in Table II extend these observations to SO_2 . It is remarkable to observe that a positive Joshi effect, as large as 17% photo-increase of current, is produced at 1.8 kV which is the lowest applied potential. As observed in the case of negative Joshi effect, the positive effect diminishes by increasing the applied kV. It is, however, interesting to observe that in the above series (Table II), but a moderate increase in the applied kV causes a precipitous decrease in the Joshi effect to practically zero; and what is significant, reverses its sign so as to give an appreciable $-\Delta i$ (see Fig. 2), at a large kV. This influence of the applied potential kV on the positive Joshi effect and the reversal of its sign are in complete accord with the results in other system (*loc. cit.*). Unlike single system, such as excited iodine and under certain conditions chlorine, it was not possible to reproduce the positive effect, mentioned above, by decreasing the applied kV to the initial low value. This may be attributed to the non-reversible change in the nature of the system as a result of the chemical decomposition produced under the discharge (Joshi and Sharma, *loc. cit.*).

Whilst due to comparatively high insulating power of SO_2 , discharge could be produced only at low gas pressure (below 180 mm.) up to 8 kV (largest used), it was observed that the decomposition produced, as judged by reduction of the over-all pressure, was about 10%, during by far the major period of Δi observations. In each of the experiments made, however, it was significant to observe a sharp decrease in the magnitude of the Joshi effect Δi during the initial stage of the discharge. Thus *e.g.*, when SO_2 was introduced in the fresh ozoniser at 24 mm. (Table I), the gas pressure diminished progressively to 22.5 mm in about 40 minutes of exposure to the discharge. During this period the relative Joshi effect, $\% \Delta i$, decreased from an initial 24 to 3, although by far the major part of SO_2 introduced remained undecomposed, as was observed subsequently by analysis of the decomposition mixture at this stage. This revealed the presence of oxygen and sulphur, both of which show the Joshi effect to an appreciable extent (*loc. cit.*). It is therefore suggested that the marked diminution (numerically) of $\% \Delta i$, as observed, may be associated with the formation of SO_3 , assuming that the corresponding influence of the traces of two other unidentified solid products of decomposition of SO_2 is negligible.

The above deduction was further tested. A fresh ozoniser was filled with purified oxygen at 99 mm. and subjected to silent discharge until an appreciable reduction of pressure was effected due to ozone formation. A moderate amount of SO_2 , purified as described already, was admitted into the annular space of the ozoniser and the mixture allowed to stand over 24 hours. The SO_3 formed by the interaction of O_3 and SO_2 condensed on the annular walls. The mixture was then topped out. On introducing various samples of pure SO_2 in this ozoniser, the Joshi effect was not detectable. Presumably, as a result of exposure to discharge under conditions during experiments, of which those in Table II are but a sample, as also the above experiments with SO_3 films, the ozoniser walls were denatured in some way with the result that the Joshi effect observed in this ozoniser became negligibly small. Even prolonged cleaning by alkali and hot chromic acid solution failed to restore Δi when the ozoniser was charged with fresh SO_2 under conditions illustrated by results in Tables I and II.

Similar results suggestive of a pronounced wall effect on the production of $\pm \Delta i$ have been observed in these laboratories (Shukla, *loc. cit.*). A series of experiments was therefore carried out to examine further the inference drawn above regarding the rôle of the wall-condensed SO_3 in inhibiting the Joshi effect.

In a fresh ozoniser, fitted with ground joint, it is seen that a pre-formed film of Na_2SO_4 does not influence markedly the Joshi effect Δi : this is, however, favoured by a coat of NaOH (Table III). What is more, the diminution of the Joshi effect with 'ageing' *i.e.*, a continuous exposure to discharge at a given applied potential(s) V does not cause a decrease of the corresponding Joshi effect as was observed in absence of an annular film (cf. Tables I and II). This is explicable since the SO_3 produced from SO_2 under the discharge, interacts with the surface alkali to form Na_2SO_4 . That a film of HgCl_2 should abolish the Joshi effect may, in part, be explained by the following suggestions due to Prof. Joshi: It is that $\pm \Delta i$ being fundamentally of surface origin (Joshi, *Curr. Sci.*, 1947, 16, 19) may be poisoned by HgS formed by the interaction of sulphur from SO_2 and HgCl_2 (Dasgupta, *unpublished data*). Furthermore, the observations on the production of the Joshi effect in hydrogen (Deshmukh, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1947, 24, 211) have shown that the presence of Hg vapour is a pronounced inhibitor in the production of Δi .

Grateful thanks of the authors are due to Professor S. S. Joshi for suggesting the problem and kind guidance.